

USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PASSING EPIC WORKS IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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Abstract. This article talks about the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the passage of epic works in literature classes, the effective methods of making the student interested in fiction and the formation of reading skills, and the issues of awakening artistic taste and thinking in the student.

Keywords: interactive method, pedagogical technology, "Brainstorming", "Networks (cluster)", "Fish" skeleton, "KZIX", "Case study", Gafur Ghulam, Entertaining boy.

In the current era of globalization, it is one of the important tasks for the teacher to make the student interested in literature and to develop the ability to read books. Because the student is getting a lot of information every day through the Internet, which is getting deeper into our lives. Therefore, the teacher should organize the lesson in such a way that the student feels the feeling of reading a work of art, talking to the characters in spirit, and not being indifferent to the fate of the characters. Only then will the teacher achieve his goal. If the teacher uses various pedagogical technologies and interactive games during the lesson, he will increase the effectiveness of the lesson. In order to use different interactive methods in the course of the lesson, it is necessary to study which pedagogical technology is more effective for which subject. Also, the correct use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process teaches the student to search for the acquired knowledge by himself, to work and analyze it independently, to draw conclusions, to work in a group. No matter what pedagogical technology the teacher uses in the classroom, he has a certain goal, that is, it is important for the student to master the taught topic in depth and be able to apply it in practice. The student, in turn, should give the result expected by the teacher. Only then will there be efficiency and development in education.

More use of "Brainstorming", "Networks (cluster)", "Fish" skeleton methods, "KZIX", "Case study" technologies in literature training will give positive results.

We will consider the pedagogical technologies mentioned above in the passage of Gafur Gulam's work.

As we know. Gafur Ghulam's work is covered in school textbooks, and academic lyceum students are familiar with the work, so the training can be started with "brainstorming". The teacher can ask students the following questions about the poet's life and work:

- 1) In what family was Gafur Ghulam born?
- 2) How was Gafur Ghulam's childhood?
- 3) What poems of Gafur Ghulam do you know?
- 4) Which of Gafur Ghulam's prose works do you know?
- 5) In the story "My thieving child", why does grandmother fondly call the thief "my thieving child"?

By asking similar questions, you can find out the students' understanding of the writer. This also helps to restore the memory of students.

And using the "Fish" skeleton when explaining a new topic to students helps to quickly remember new information by seeing and hearing:

Distribute the table to students and allow them to complete it themselves. After a certain time, the correct option of the table should be displayed on the screen. In this case, the student analyzes his own mistakes. This teaches the student to think independently and work on mistakes.

Analyzing the writer's story "Shum Bola" together with the students through the "Case Study" technology will help to get deeper into the work. Working with a small group works well for this. Well, let's give a brief information about what kind of technology "Case study" is: "Case study" is a method of analyzing problematic situations and concrete situations study) is based on the organization of usual situations taken in life or artificially created situations and directs learners to express the problem and search for an appropriate solution.

We can also observe the cross-disciplinary connection by giving group 1 the episode about "Madmen in Tashkent" at the beginning of the work as a problem situation. Through the events in the work, the students think about the hardships our nation was going through from the beginning, and the extremely difficult way of life.

Type of problem situation	Causes of the problematic situation	Actions to get out of the situation
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<p>One of the joyous pastimes for us children, who were stuck in the market, was the bazaar, neighborhood, and street crazy people. There were so many madmen in Tashkent that you couldn't count them all. The boy tells why the madmen are mad. How do you explain it?</p>		
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For the 2nd group, we refer the readers to the episode about cunning, sly people like the thief Sultan, who make fools of simple people, laugh at them, and play with them as puppets. In this predicament, readers must expose Sultan the Thief or set him on the right path. This helps the students to judge what is right and what is wrong.

Type of problem situation	Causes of the Problematic situation	Actions to get out of the situation
<p>In the middle was the famous thief Sultan from the neighborhood of Kogurmoch. This time, he was holding a young man with tears in his eyes, not as a thief, but as a poor victim of a robbery. How do you explain it?</p>		

For group 3, the episode of Shum's childhood friend Amon and Domla's dead washing can be given as a problematic situation. In this, students will have to analyze the sad life of teenagers who are ready to do any work to earn a living.

Type of problem situation	Causes of the Problematic situation	Actions to get out of the situation
<p>Amon, who was walking in front of me, suddenly threw himself back, made a "squeal" sound and lost his temper. The teacher stepped back and left the room he froze in front of the door. As soon as I looked at the dead body, I understood the reason why Amon was lost. With which eye we looked, the dead man we wanted to wash was resurrected. How do you explain it?</p>		

During the lesson, many such problematic situations can be cited from the play. This helps students to understand the topic quickly and easily. They also learn to draw conclusions from the work, think independently, and express their thoughts correctly. Having analyzed the above-mentioned problematic situations in the work, the reader understands that "Shum bola" is not just an adventure work, but a scene from the darkest days of our past, and reads it with interest with a sense of gratitude for the opportunities created for the youth.

If every lesson in literary subjects is organized in this way, students' enthusiasm for reading works of art increases day by day.

REFERENCES

1. Uzbek language and literature educational journal 2020y. 8th edition.
2. G. Gulam collection of “You are not orphan”
3. N.Hotamov, B. Sarimsoqov “Russian-Uzbek” explanatory dictionary of literary terms. Tashkent “O’qituvchi”-1983y.
4. Ishmuhamedov R, Abduqodirov. A, Pardayev.A. Innovative technologies in education.Tashkent-2008y.
5. QUNDUZKHON HUSANBOYEVA, ROZA NIYOZMETOVA. METHOD OF TEACHING LITERATURE Tashkent – 2018